

FEATURES OF CONNECTION OF ECOLOGICAL SOCIAL REALITY WITH PRIORITY NEEDS

Dumarova Gulfira Kozimbekovna

Madaminov Zohidjon Yunusovich

Teacher of the Department of Social Humanities, Pedagogy and Psychology of the Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

+9989997601384 // +998916070084

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Abstract. This article discusses aspects of the social psychological features of the formation of attitudes to social reality in young people. The psychological features of the formation of social reality in relation to the needs of the priority person were determined by conducting A. Maslow's methodology. Perceptions of social reality also tend to change at a time when priority satisfaction is declining. Already needs are one of the main determinants of human behavior

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Introduction

The great economic and anthropological crisis, various interethnic and interreligious conflicts, terrorism and extremism have led to the collapse of individual and cohesive human reality, the alienation of the individual from the meaning and activities of private life, and, ultimately, the rise of priority needs. leading to a change in the structure of terminal values related to human life.

Perceptions of social reality also tend to change at a time when priority satisfaction is declining. Already needs are one of the main determinants of human behavior. A. Maslow's concept of the hierarchy of needs consists of the following main ideas:

- Man always feels the need for something;
- The person is in a whirlpool of obvious needs that allow grouping;
- Need groups have a hierarchical (gradual) view of each other;
- Lack of needs motivates a person to act; those who are satisfied have no motivating power;
- if any need is met, it is replaced by another;
- usually a person can feel different needs that interact in a complex way;
- needs close to the lowest level of the hierarchy must be met first; high-level needs begin to have an active impact on a person once low-level needs are met;
- The ability to meet high-level needs is wider than the ability to meet low-level needs.

In his work On the Psychology of Reality, Maslow added a list of higher needs to what he called the need for perfection. However, Maslow himself acknowledged that it was difficult to define these needs because it was difficult for them to fully differentiate from each other in common. According to Maslow, the values of reality include such values as simplicity, simplicity, perfection, beauty, completeness, justice, vitality, originality, sincerity, honesty. The

values of reality belong to the structure of development as an individual and become powerful motives of human activity.

Many scholars describe need as an internal condition caused by the need for objects necessary for the existence and development of the individual. Clayton Alderfer, for example, like Maslow, in his theory relies on the view that human needs can be grouped into separate groups. But he points out that there are three groups of needs: availability needs, 2) the need to bond, 3) the need for perfection.

The need groups mentioned in this theory are similar to the need groups in Maslow's theory. Availability needs include two categories of needs in Maslow's tree of needs: security needs (other than group security needs) and physiological needs. There is a commonality between the need to bond and the need for belonging and involvement.

According to Alderfer's theory, the hierarchy of needs rises from explicit needs to uncertain needs, and each time the needs are not met, attention begins to shift to a simpler level of need. In the tree of needs, upward movement is called the process of meeting needs, and downward movement is called frustration. The existence of a two-pronged approach to meeting needs provides additional opportunities to motivate a person.

In psychological sources, the following manifestations of basic needs are distinguished: biological, social, and spiritual. Biological needs depend on the vital natural and material conditions of human life, and their social needs are reflected in human needs such as labor, communication, and community recognition. Spiritual needs are related to the need to become acquainted with knowledge, religious and artistic values. Many authors argue that in extreme life situations involving the transition from one economic formation to another, it is manifested primarily in biological needs such as safety, protection of one's mental and physiological health, as well as the ability of oneself and one's loved ones to live normally.

Hence, the purpose of this part of our empirical research is to determine which priority needs are related to the appearance of attitudes toward social reality. In order to study the relationship of a person's priority needs with social reality, we used the questionnaire "Determination of the level of satisfaction of needs" (double comparison method) developed by VV Skvortsov on the basis of A. Maslow's theory "Tree of Needs".

Results and Discussion.

We first asked respondents according to their forms of attitude to social reality: People: conservation-change; Items: conservation-change; Location: conservation-change; Organization: conservation-change; Information: conservation-change - grouped. Participants in the study were classified at this stage according to three age groups: 20-25 year olds (160 boys and 210 girls), 35-45 year olds (170 men, 200 women), and the last class was over 45 years old. (160 men, 210 women). It has been studied not only in terms of gender differences, but also in terms of age. Respondents included in these groups were divided into two subgroups: high and low scores.

Table 1

The composition of respondents distributed according to the form of attitude to social reality (conservation-change)

Components of social reality	Name of groups	Gender	Number
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People: conservation-change	People: conservation	20-25 years old	73
		35-40 years old	69
		45 years old	88
	People: change	20-25 years old	58
		35-45 years old	71
		45 years old	44
Items: conservation-change	Items: conservation	20-25 years old	111
		35-45 years old	51
		45 years old	108
	Items: change	20-25 years old	48
		35-45 years old	99
		45 years old	51
Location: conservation-change	Location: conservation	20-25 years old	14
		35-45 years old	33
		45 years old	77
	Location: change	20-25 years old	41
		35-45 years old	26
		45 years old	39
Organization: conservation-change	Organization: conservation	20-25 years old	43
		35-45 years old	71
		45 years old	82
	Organization: change	20-25 years old	75
		35-45 years old	38
		45 years old	60
Information: conservation-change	Information: conservation	20-25 years old	67
		35-45 years old	75
		45 years old	79
	Information: change	20-25 years old	77
		35-45 years old	81
		45 years old	35

The levels of satisfaction of the priority needs of the participants, distributed according to the perception of social reality according to these age periods, were compared.

The results show that the aspect of social reality in relation to human relations (conservation-change) is associated with the priority needs of the individual at different ages: material needs (high salary, material convenience, purchase of modern items) completely unsatisfied statistically significant 25-45 years and older, "people" prone respondents (25-45 years old "People: conservation" - $x = 25.9 \pm 2.14$ and "People: renewal" - $x = 27.2 \pm 1.94$, $p \leq 0.05$; over 45 years old in respondents "People: conservation" - $x = 23.6 \pm 0.81$ and "People: renewal" - $x = 27.8 \pm 1.99$, $p \leq 0.01$).

When we studied the relationship between social reality and the relationship (conception-change) to the place (place of residence) with the needs of the individual in the age group, we noted the following: The statistical difference in the feeling of not satisfying the

material needs is different from the group of respondents in the age group of 25-45 years.) is related to the increase in social awareness (in the 20-25-year-old respondents, "Space: conception" - $x=24.3\pm 1.01$ and "Space: renewal" - $x=26.7\pm 2.11$ $p \leq 0, 01$; "Space: conception" - $x=24.4\pm 2.91$ and "Space: renewal" - $x=25.09\pm 3.02$ $p\leq 0.01$) among respondents over 45 years old. Feeling that the need for security is not fully met was statistically significantly higher only in respondents over 45 years old who tend to change their residential area ("Space: conception" - $x=27.02\pm 3.18$ and "Space: renewal" - $x=30.01\pm 2.06$, $p \leq 0.01$). It was observed that the need to develop personal relationships seems to be completely unsatisfied in many respondents over 45 years old ("Space: conception" - $x=28.9\pm 1.76$ and "Space: renewal" - $x=28.02\pm 1.88$ $p \leq 0, 01$).

We can see that the need for recognition does not change the attitude of the respondent to the social reality in the form of conception-change. It was found that the need for self-actualization is highly dependent on the attitude of the respondent aged 25-45 to the social reality ("Space: conception" - $x=21.4\pm 2.81$ and "Space: renewal" - $x=22.8\pm 3.91$ $p \leq 0.05$).

It should be noted that if the need for security did not cover the perception of the main social reality of the 20-25-year-old respondents, the 25-45-year-old respondents and over 45-year-old respondents strengthened their focus on renewing the working organization (in the 25-45-year-old respondents "Organization: Conception" - $x=17.8\pm 1.29$ and "Organization: renewal" - $x=20.1\pm 2.3$ $p \leq 0.01$; "Organization: conception" - $x=26.98 \pm 1$ in the respondents over 45 years old, 03 and "Organization: update" - $x=29.2 \pm 1.68$ $p\leq 0.01$).

It is observed that social need is related only to the change in the organization in which the respondent over 45 years old works (in respondents over 45 years old, "Organization: conception" - $x=26.3 \pm 2.76$ and "Organization: renewal" - $x=28.5 \pm 2, 44$ $p\leq 0.01$). On the other hand, the need to be recognized led to a change in the social identity aspect of the 25-45-year-old respondent, which did not find expression in the identity characteristics of the working organization of the 20-25-year-old respondent, nor over 45-year-old respondent (in the 25-45-year-old respondent, "Organization: conception" - $x=26.6 \pm 1.04$ and "Organization: renewal" - $x=28.8 \pm 2.88$ $p\leq 0.05$). Finally, if the need for self-actualization was not reflected in the social identity characteristics of the respondents aged 20-25, the respondents aged 25-45 and those over 45 changed their orientation to a certain extent in relation to changing the organization in which they work (in the respondents aged 25-45, "Organization : conception" - $x=21.2 \pm 1.76$ and "Organization: renewal" - $x=22.9 \pm 2.44$ $p\leq 0.01$, in the respondent's lap over 45 years old "Organization: conception" - $x=23.67 \pm 2.11$ and "Organization: update" - $x=25.07 \pm 2.94$ $p\leq 0.05$).

Conclusion

As we hypothesized, priority needs were found to affect the social cognitive characteristics of respondents of different ages according to a certain pattern. Material needs have the same effect on all forms of social cognition at all ages. The fact that the features of social cognition are not to some extent related to the needs of auto-actualization proves the need to study this need as a separate phenomenon.

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